

THE CONCEPT OF LIMITED SANITY IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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Abstract There is no sharp line between full mental health and the state of insanity. Various scholars, not only in the field of jurisprudence, but in the field of psychiatry have repeatedly wondered about the gap between insanity and sanity. In this regard, a legitimate legal question arises about the responsibility of a person who committed an act that carries social danger in the so-called intermediate state: between normal mental health and pathology. Such a pathological condition, some authors call reduced sanity, others - limited, and others - border sanity.

Keywords: limited sanity, Criminal Code, reduced, Western Europe, criminal type, criminal offense.

For the first time, the term “limited sanity” began to be used in the 19th century in the criminal law of Romano-German states. The second half of the 19th century is precisely characterized by the transition to the formulation and solution of the problems of individualization of criminal liability, both in general and in relation to persons with mental anomalies based on a systematic purposeful study of the laws, both external and internal determinants of the formation of a “criminal” type.

Uzbek criminal law did not know such a concept. Subsequently, a response on this issue appeared in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, namely, Art. 18¹ of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan - “Responsibility of a person suffering from a mental disorder that does not exclude sanity”, according to which a sane person who at the time of committing a crime due to a mental disorder could not fully realize the significance of his actions (inaction) or supervise them, is liable, and the second paragraph - for a person suffering from a mental disorder that

does not exclude sanity, a court may impose compulsory medical measures along with punishment. This article describes the institution, which is usually referred to in the doctrinal literature as “reduced” sanity.

In connection with the need to carry out a comprehensive analysis of the historical formation and development of the problem of limited sanity, one should turn to the foreign experience of introducing this institution into criminal law. It should be noted that a number of Western European states have for many years provided for the institution of limited sanity in their criminal law. In particular, the criminal codes of Japan, Denmark, Switzerland, Italy and Finland contain the institution of limited sanity in their articles. The broadest and most indicative in this regard is the Swiss Criminal Code of 1937. According to Art. 11 of the specified Criminal Code, reduced sanity is considered established if, due to a disturbance in mental activity or consciousness, or due to insufficient mental development, the offender, at the time of the commission of the act, did not have the full ability to assess the wrongfulness of his behavior and be guided by this assessment [1, p. 147]. According to the judicial practice under this article, the court, at its discretion, commutes the punishment of such a person, and, according to experts, has the right to decide on the placement of the accused in a medical facility.

However, back in the middle of the XVIII century. In Western Europe, the mentally ill were punished and condemned along with mentally healthy and healthy criminals. At that time, the court did not set itself the task of ascertaining the state of mental health of the defendant, his emotional excitement, or any other mentally unstable state. Subsequently, the scientific works and practical activities of the founder of the classical school of criminal law, C. Beccaria, were so obvious and led to the fact that lawyers really had to think about the problem of sanity or insanity of the person who committed the crime [2, p. 21].

The first reference to the institution of insanity appeared in Art. 64 of the French Penal Code of 1810, according to which: “there is no crime, no misconduct

if during the commission of the crime the accused was in a state of insanity” [3, p. 26]. In the future, this norm was borrowed by some European states.

Shortly after lawyers and psychiatrists discovered the concepts of sanity and insanity, it turned out that between these states there is a large group of people who are essentially sane when committing a socially dangerous act, but they reveal some mental deviations that are somehow This affects their behavior. It is these features of mental states that prompted jurists to study and develop the concept of limited sanity.

At the beginning of the XX century, the famous forensic scientist Enrico Ferrero deduced the classification of criminals, having contributed by his work to the institution of limited sanity. He identified three categories of persons:

1. Crazy or half-crazy - mattoids;
2. Irreparable or natural;
3. Familiar - those who began criminal activity from childhood.

It is the first point of his classification - this is the type between the sick and the healthy. According to the author, they are distinguished by dementia, in connection with which they commit cold-blooded crimes [4, p. 28].

For the first time, limited sanity is mentioned in the criminal codes of the German states: the Saxon Penal Code of 1841, the Hessian Penal Code of 1841, the Bavarian Penal Code of 1848, the Turenge Penal Code of 1850 and others. All of them contained similar factors causing limited sanity and reduction punishment with its presence, namely: dementia, old age, developmental delay, lack of education, extremely unfavorable or corrupting situation in childhood [5, p. 58].

It is also worth paying a little attention to the legislation of the former Soviet republics. I would like to note that in most countries the institution of limited sanity takes place in the criminal law. In most of them, this norm carries the onset of criminal liability, or measures of a compulsory medical nature, for example, the criminal code of the Republic of Belarus, the Azerbaijan Republic, and Tajikistan.

In the Latvian Criminal Code, the norm of limited sanity allows the law enforcer to choose a measure of punishment up to its complete exclusion. “If a person, when committing a criminal offense due to mental disorders or mental retardation, could not fully realize his actions, being in a state of limited sanity, depending on certain circumstances, the court can commute the sentence or release him from it” [6, p. 283].

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